

Multi-band digital radars based on photonics

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Introduction

- Most radars usually realize *narrow-band* measures
- Microwave Photonics enables broadband capabilities (and high precision)
- These are translated into a novel and large flexibility
- Flexibility enables broadband measures!

Outline

- Motivations for Photonics in radar systems
- The Photonics-based radar
- Field trials
- Evolutions of the Photonics-based radar
 - Bi-band Photonics-based radar
 - Radar-Lidar system
- What's next?

Motivations for Photonics in radar systems

Current radar systems scenario

- Different functionalities are exploited via different systems:
 - ✓ Different carrier frequency
 - ✓ Different waveforms
 - ✓ Different bandwidth
 - ✓
- Currently each apparatus works in specific conditions
- The performance gets worse as the RF frequency increases

Future concept: Multifunction radar

- A **multifunction radar** is a single unit operating in **more than one band**, implementing **more than one function**: target detection and identification, tracking, discrimination on a large number of targets as well as environmental mapping, communication links etc. etc..

Issues with Electronics

Multifunction radar requires a **Software Defined Radio (SDR)** approach

SDR **signal generation** requires **synthesizers** with:

- Wide bandwidth
- Waveform flexibility
- Carrier frequency flexibility (up to mmW)
- Superior phase stability

SDR **signal receiver** requires **ADC** with:

- Large input bandwidth
- High sampling rates
- High sensitivity and dynamic range (SNR & SFDR)
- High quality of the digitized signal (ENOB)

All these requirements represent issues for the current electronics devices

Issues with Electronics

- Today's best **digital synthesizers** are available only at low frequency (few GHz) and they require analog up-conversion stages using mixers which introduces **phase noise and distortions**
- Today's best **ADCs** show only few GHz of analog BW, with a sampling clock aperture **jitter** of hundreds of femtoseconds

Benefits of Photonics in radars

- ✓ **Transport**
 - *Low loss*
 - *Low distortions*
 - *EMI free*
- ✓ **Generation**
 - *Frequency flexibility (DC to 60 GHz)*
 - *Agile RF frequency variation*
- ✓ **Detection**
 - *Extremely high stability*
 - *Multiple simultaneous carriers*
- ✓ **Elaboration**
 - *Wide bandwidth*
 - *Adaptability*
 - *Multiple functionalities*

Potentials of Photonics in radars

- Fully digital system, reconfigurability (SDR)
- Multi-band operations
- Integration of Surveillance and Communications

The Photonics-based radar

The first Photonics-based radar

- **PHODIR** project (2009-2013):
Starting Grant of ERC funded to Antonella Bogoni at CNIT

The first Photonics-based radar

- PHODIR project (2008-2012)
Starting Grant of ERC

Photonics-based RF generation

- Based on heterodyning of modes selected from a MLL

Photonics-based RF generation

Chirped radar pulses @10GHz and @40GHz

Photonics-based RF detection

- Based on optical under-sampling

Photonics-based RF detection

PHODIR transceiver specs

Parameter	Photonics-based transceiver	State of the art electronics transceiver
<i>Transmitter</i>		
Carrier frequency	Flexible direct generation up to 40GHz	Direct generation below 2GHz up-conversions above 2GHz
Signal jitter	<15fs integrated in [10kHz-10MHz]	Typical >20fs integrated in [10kHz-10MHz]
Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR)	>73dB/MHz	>80dB/MHz
Spurious-free dynamic range (SFDR)	>70dBc	>70dBc
Instantaneous bandwidth	200MHz, easily extendable with MLL at higher repetition rate	<2GHz
<i>Receiver</i>		
Input carrier frequency	up to 40GHz with direct RF undersampling	<2GHz down-conversions at higher frequencies
Instantaneous bandwidth	200MHz, easily extendable with MLL at higher repetition rate	<2GHz
Sampling jitter	<10fs integrated in [10kHz-10MHz]	Typical >100fs integrated in [10kHz-10MHz]
Spurious-free dynamic range (SFDR)	50dB	>70dB
Effective number of bits (ENOB)	>7 for carrier frequency up to 40GHz	<8 for carrier frequency <2GHz

Field trials

Aerial scenario, fixed antenna

- Using a front-end in the X-band
- Changing pulse modulation to adjust the resolution

a)

b) Velocity [km/h] Range [km]

c) Velocity [km/h] Range [km]

d) R = 5400m ΔR = 150m

e) R = 6072m ΔR = 23m

Aerial scenario, fixed antenna

- Comparing PHODIR with the radar at the PISA AIRPORT
- With the technical support of the Italian Aeronautics

	46 th Brigade	PhoDiR
Radar Location	43°41'29"N 10°23'27"E	43°34'50"N 10°18'00"E
Tracking	214°	N.A.
Range	17.2km	3.25km
Velocity	153kn	140kn
Altitude	2000ft	N.A.

Maritime scenario, fixed antenna

- Radar site: Livorno Port (Tuscany - Italy)
- With the support of the Livorno Port Authorities

Long-range detection

PW	1 μ s\barker13 ($\Delta R=11m$)
P _{Peak}	40W
PRF	5KHz
CIT	100msec ($\Delta f=10Hz$)

Harbour protection

Maritime scenario, rotating antenna

- Radar site: Port of S.Benedetto del Tronto (Italy)
- Direct comparison with a commercial radar

GEM elettronica

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Maritime scenario, rotating antenna

In collaboration with

GEM elettronica

Maritime scenario, rotating antenna

Comparison with a commercial X-band coherent radar

In collaboration with GEM elettronica

Performance comparison

NF: Noise Figure
MDS: Minimum detectable signal

Evolutions of the Photonics-based radar

Connecting Minds. Exchanging Ideas.

WSP: Microwave photonics for broadband measurement
IMS2015, Phoenix, AZ, 17-22 May, 2015

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Novel possibilities

- The photonic core enables a **unique feature**:
the implementation of several **coherent radars** on **multiple bands**
- The shared photonic core allows **reducing the cost and SWaP**
- The coherence allows **improving the data fusion** for increased resolution
- The flexibility enables implementing a **multi-band cognitive SDR system**

Adapt the sensor to the environments and targets

COGNITIVE SENSOR

1. *Observe the scene*
2. *Receive information*
3. *Think, evaluate, decide*
4. *Adapt*

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Coherent bi-band radar

Laser
Photonics-based bi-band transceiver

S-band front-end

Acquisition board

X-band front-end

Bi-band radar with data fusion

Coherent radar-lidar system

Additional features:

- Detect, Track, or Image functions
- Short and Long range detection
- High resolution in range and cross range
- Data fusion algorithms

Radar-lidar preliminary results

- Multi-frequency LIDAR technique to avoid speckle noise
- Lidar @ 10, 30, 40 GHz
- Radar @ 10 GHz

What's next?

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Next technical developments

- For maximum flexibility, the implementation with **integrated photonic techniques** is necessary
 - Tunable and very selective optical filters
 - Environmental stability
 - Reduced SWaP
- For field deployment, **specific laser sources** should be developed
 - Stable, robust, efficient, cheap
- For maximum take-over of peculiar features, **advanced digital processing** must be implemented
 - Real-time processing
 - Improved precision thanks to coherence
 - Cognitive real-time adaptability

Connecting Minds. Exchanging Ideas.

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Next functionalities

- **Photonic beamforming** can be easily included in the system
 - Broadband true time delay
 - The RF signal is already in the optical domain, avoid EO and OE conversions

- The flexibility can allow the **integration of surveillance and communications**

Thank you!

